

Modeling the Effects of Salt Loop Flow Rate on Molten Salt Reactor Off-gas Isotopics

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803166

ABSTRACT

Liquid-fueled molten salt reactors (MSRs) are a reactor design in which fuel and fission products are continuously transported throughout a flow loop. This leads to a pressure buildup due to fission gases that must be removed from the reactor vessel. The concept of an off-gas system (OGS) was introduced to accomplish this by removing volatile fission products. This removal gives a unique chance to gain information about the operation of the reactor by examining the fission products removed by the OGS. To improve modeling fidelity of an MSR off-gas system, this study investigates the impact of modeling the salt flow loop on off-gas isotopics. A three-region flow loop with a six-region OGS was designed in OpenMC and run as a zero-dimensional problem. The noble gases krypton and xenon were transferred to the OGS from a region of the flow loop that was not subjected to neutron flux. The isotopics recorded in the three regions of the loop and the first region of the OGS were then compared across flow rates from 1/100th that of the MSRE to 10 times that of the MSRE. The results of the multi-region flow loop were compared to an identical model with a single region representing the entire loop. This preliminary comparison indicates that flow modeling may not be necessary for accurate OGS quantities of isotopes with half-lives much greater than the loop cycle time.

Keywords: molten salt reactor, off-gas, flow loop, radionuclides, flow loop

1. INTRODUCTION

The flowing fuel in a molten salt reactor (MSR) presents a complex modeling challenge surrounding the fission products' distribution. Accurate representation of the concentrations of key isotopes in an MSR requires high-fidelity two-phase fluid flow simulations in combination with neutronics and chemistry solvers. The primary mechanism used to alleviate pressure buildup in an MSR is the circulation of an inert "cover gas" through a space in the reactor where it can interface with the fuel salt. Volatile fission products may then escape the fuel salt and be carried away into the OGS for processing and decay.

Isotopes of interest for the OGS are gaseous fission products with strong impact on neutronics, such as ¹³⁵Xe. Due to its large thermal neutron capture cross-section, ¹³⁵Xe acts as a reactivity poison by absorbing neutrons in the core, reducing the neutron economy of the core. Xenon is produced in a reactor system in small part directly from nuclear fission, but is primarily produced through the decay of ¹³⁵I and ^{135m}Xe. It is of interest to understand the rate at which xenon is being removed from the system by the OGS to better model the xenon poisoning of the core.

To accurately characterize the OGS, a model must be created that simulates the removal of nuclides into the cover gas. Previous work has shown that the off-gas isotopics can be solved for analytically in a simplified MSR model if no flow is assumed [1]. However, it has also been shown that the concentration

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of nuclides throughout the flow loop of an MSR is not necessarily homogeneous for radionuclides with half-lives on the timescale of the loop residence time and/or those that can be chemically removed from the fuel salt within the primary loop [2] [3]. Additionally, very low flow rates would cause long nuclide residence times outside the core, allowing them to decay and appreciably change the isotopics of the fuel salt. However, due to the high volumetric flow rates of MSRs, this is unlikely to exist in a real system. If the flow rates are high enough, it may not be necessary to model the fluid flow of the fuel salt through a loop to obtain accurate off-gas isotopics.

This work aims to compare the off-gas isotopics obtained from (1) a model with one representative region for the whole loop with (2) those obtained from a three-region flowing loop to investigate the relationship of off-gas isotopics with loop flow rate.

2. MSR MODEL DESCRIPTION

To compare the impact of flow rate on MSR off-gas isotopics, two different models were created using OpenMC, an open-source, community-developed Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code [4]. The methodology and blueprint for these models rely heavily on similar modeling work done previously [5]. Each model is composed of two distinct regions: the off-gas system (OGS) and the flow loop. The difference between the two models exists in the way the flow loop is modeled. In the first model, the “one-region loop” model, the flow loop is modeled as a single volume that contains the entire volume of salt. This one-region loop is subject to a constant neutron flux that is incident on the entire salt during the simulation. This is different from a real MSR system in which the volume of salt not present in the core experiences far less flux. The second model, the “multi-region loop” model, contains three volumes to represent the flow loop: the “Core”, “Pipe A,” and “Pipe B.” Figure 1 describes the two models. Both models contain an identical six-region OGS intended to mirror the flow path and tanks used by the MSRE [6].

The choice of a three-region loop was made to keep complexity and computational costs low, while also allowing for a reasonable description of the MSRE flow loop and account for the salt’s flow outside of the core. These three regions represent the necessary processes involved in the simulation of an off-gas system. The fission product inventory is generated in the core. Fission gases are removed from the system outside of the core in Pipe A and transferred to the OGS pump bowl. Lastly, in Pipe B, the remaining fission products are then allowed some additional out-of-core decay time without the effects of flux or removal to the OGS. The volumes of the three-region loop were estimated from thermal hydraulic data taken at ten positions along the MSRE primary loop [7] and simplified for the three-region 0D-flow loop modeled here. A comparison of these three regions with the one-region volume can be seen in Table I. The total volumes of the six OGS regions can be seen in Table II. The six regions are the pump bowl, the jumper liner, the decay tank, charcoal bed one, charcoal bed two, and the final tank.

Table I. Volume fractions in the core.

Model	Total salt volume (cm ³)	Core	Pipe A	Pipe B
One-region Loop	449.7	1.000	-	-
Multi-region Loop	449.7	0.3402	0.2111	0.4487

Table II. Volumes in the OGS (for both models), with abbreviations from Figure 1.

Model	PB (cm ³)	JL (cm ³)	DT (cm ³)	CB1 (cm ³)	CB2 (cm ³)	FT (cm ³)
Both	1.206E+01	6.779E-01	8.684E+01	2.084E+03	9.379E+04	2.193E+02

Figure 1. Single-region fuel salt flow diagram.

The two systems can be represented easily with a set of differential equations. The first system, with a single core region, can be represented by the one-group Bateman equations given by Equations 1 and 2.

$$\text{One-region core model: } \frac{dC_i^{core}}{dt} = y_i \Sigma_f \phi + \sum_j (\lambda_{j \rightarrow i} C_j^{core}) - (\lambda_i + \sigma_i^a \phi - \epsilon_i \frac{V^A}{V_{tot}}) C_i^{core} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{OGS model: } \frac{dC_i^u}{dt} = \sum_j (\lambda_{j \rightarrow i} C_j^u) - \lambda_i C_i^u - f_{OGS}^{u \rightarrow v} C_i^u + f_{OGS}^{w \rightarrow u} C_i^w \quad (2)$$

The f terms are fractional flow rates between the different regions of a given loop and ϵ_i is a fractional removal rate to the OGS pumpbowl. Both rates are in units of inverse seconds. The fractional flow rates in the models is calculated simply by

$$f_x^{u \rightarrow v} = (t^u)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where t^u is the residence time in region u [7]. In Equation 2, u represents the section of the off-gas described by the equation, w represents the preceding region, and v represents the next region. These can be seen in Figure 1. For example, in the rate equation governing the off-gas jumper line, $OGS2_JL$, u would be $OGS2_JL$, w would be $OGS1_PB$, and v would be $OGS3_DT$.

The scenario for which the control flow rates are used will be described as $v = v_{MSRE}$ as the calculated fractional flow rates are all based on MSRE values. The values for the control fractional flow rates in s^{-1} (f) are given in Table III. The baseline value for the removal term is taken from the literature stating a liquid stripping coefficient of 240 ft³/hr [8]. The OGS removal rate was calculated from this value by dividing it by the volume of the region subject to removal: the whole salt for the one-region loop model and Pipe A for the multi-region loop model. Due to the difference in the two volumes subject to removal, ϵ is different for the two models, seen in Table III.

The multi-region model is described mathematically in almost the same way as the one-region model, with two additional terms to include the flow into and out of each loop region. The Bateman equation

Table III. Control flow rates in the multi-region model.

Region	Control fractional flow rate (f) (s^{-1})
Core	1.14E-01
Pipe A	1.83E-01
Pipe B	8.63E-02
One-region ϵ	9.64E-04
Multiregion ϵ	4.57E-03

for the core region in the multi-region loop is given in Equation 4. The same methodology is extended to the other regions, with Equation 2 also describing the multi-region loop OGS.

$$\text{Multi-region model: } \frac{dC_i^{core}}{dt} = y_i \Sigma_f \phi + \sum_j (\lambda_{j \rightarrow i} C_j^{core}) - (\lambda_i + f_{salt}^{core \rightarrow A} + \sigma_i^a \phi) C_i^{core} + f_{salt}^{B \rightarrow core} C_i^B \quad (4)$$

3. SIMULATION

OpenMC allows for point depletion through the use of its *IndependentOperator* class, which relies on user-provided microscopic cross-sections and fluxes (previously generated with an OpenMC core geometry) to bypass the need for neutron transport-coupled depletion. The depletion solver utilized by OpenMC is the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method combined with a constant flux approximation [4]. The parameters used in this transport-independent depletion are listed in Table IV. Only the core material was subject to the one-group flux, while the rest of the materials experienced no flux. For both models, a unit cell model was designed in OpenMC representing a quarter of a fuel channel in the MSRE. The material composition of this fuel was taken from an ongoing MSRE fuel depletion benchmark model [9]. OpenMC's "get_microxs_and_fluxes" method was used to generate the one-group cross-sections and fluxes in the fuel salt and graphite. These cross-sections and fluxes were used in both models. The models are designed as scaled models of the MSRE with the total volume of each region of the system being scaled by 1/4560, representing the ratio of the volume of the fuel region in the unit cell model to that in the actual MSRE core lattice channels. The simulation input power was calculated using the maximum thermal power output of the MSRE, given as 7.4MW [10]. Scaling this thermal power by our geometry scaling factor of 1/4560, we obtain the value 1623W seen in Table IV.

Table IV. OpenMC depletion parameters.

Parameter	One-group Flux	Power	Cycles (Inactive)	Particles/cycle	Step size (s) (# of steps)
Value	82.2 $\frac{n-cm}{source}$	1623 W	150 (50)	10 ⁵	3.64E+05 (20)

A series of simulations were run in which the flow rate of the fuel salt was varied and the isotopics of the OGS pump bowl examined. Flow rate variation was made possible through OpenMC's ability to include a fractional transfer of elements between materials as leveraged in the previous equations. The pump bowl is the only region examined for the OGS in this study because the two models have identical OGS residence times meaning that differences seen in the first region (the pump bowl) will persist throughout the rest of the system.

In total, five cases were run in addition to a control run that utilized v_{MSRE} . The flow rates tested, relative to the control flow rate, were $10v_{MSRE}$, v_{MSRE} , $v_{MSRE}/10$, and $v_{MSRE}/100$. Only one test was run for the one-region loop as there is no flow to scale. The choice to include several slower flow rates

was made to examine the impact of longer decay time for isotopes in the loop on their concentrations in the OGS. Conversely, the higher flow speeds would tend to all show the same behavior as the transfer from the core to Pipe A becomes high. Still, for short-lived isotopes, this can be relevant.

3.1. Results and Analysis

Noble gas fission product concentration differences between the one-region and multi-region loop models is the metric by which the results will be judged. This class of elements is very commonly found as a fission product and will have a high concentration in the salt. Noble gases are also the class of element with the highest tendency to leave the salt and enter the OGS due to their inert chemical properties. ^{135}Xe , an important reactivity poison and a key target for removal, is also a noble gas. Thus, the present study focuses only on removing the elements krypton and xenon into the pumpbowl.

Figures 2 and 3 show the depletion results in units of atom density of ^{135}Xe for all relevant regions at the chosen flow rates. The one-region model does not contain a Pipe A region, and so the plotted concentration for the one-region model in these Figures is simply the atom density in the core. This was done because the purpose of the one-region model is the consolidation of the entire salt material into a single region. This is equivalent to assuming homogeneous concentrations throughout the loop. The expected buildup of fission products is seen with equilibrium being reached at around 20,000 seconds. The percent differences between the multiregion model and the one-region model at every location of interest and at every flow rate tests are shown in Figures 4. The percent difference in the flow rates was calculated using the equilibrium value of each flow rate simulation and by taking the multi-region loop model's result to be the "theoretical" value as it should represent the most accurate flow modeling. These percent differences are given for the isotopes ^{135}Xe and ^{91}Kr . These two isotopes were chosen due to their large difference in half-life allowing us to investigate the affects of flow rate with changing half-life.

Figure 2. The atom densities of ^{135}Xe in the Core and Pipe A across the depletion for varying salt flow rates.

It is clear from the ^{135}Xe results that at sufficiently high flow rates relative to the isotope's half-life, the off-gas concentrations of the one-region core model agree with the multi-region loop model (seen in Figure 3 in the Pump Bowl and in Figure 4). This behavior suggests that isotopes with long half-lives relative to the loop period will be less sensitive to salt flow rate overall. The results in Figure 2 also indicate that the presence of an off-gas system with ϵ on the order of $1\text{E-}03\text{s}^{-1}$ causes the long-term concentration of ^{135}Xe at the site of removal to be effectively independent of the salt loop's flow rate.

Figure 3. The atom densities of ^{135}Xe in Pipe B and in the pump bowl across the depletion for varying salt flow rates.

Figure 4. The percent difference in the ^{135}Xe concentration in the one-region and multi-region models as a function of flow rate multiplier.

^{91}Kr , however, with its very short 8.5 second half-life, will not see a degree of convergence great enough to produce a flow rate-invariant OGS concentration curve, as shown in Figure 4 with high percent differences for all flow rates. This short half-life will also cause the one-region core model to produce different results than the multi-region loop, indicating that flow modeling or implementing a correction factor is necessary. These results indicate that there are scenarios in which it is necessary to model the flow loop to obtain accurate off-gas isotopics depending on the half-lives of the relevant isotopes of interest.

It is expected that a difference in concentration between regions would arise due to flow rate changes, as longer residence time in Pipe A, while irrelevant for ^{135}Xe decay, would lead to differing removal to the off-gas system. An attempt was made to model the scenario by building the burnup matrix manually, and the same behavior was observed in this verification problem. It was noticed that when the flow rate

and ε terms became similar in magnitude, the curves representing concentration (Figure 2) exhibited convergent behavior. However, once the OGS removal term dominates (i.e., at very low flow rate), slight differences in the Pipe A material begin to appear, shown by the data for $\nu_{MSRE}/100$. Though, even at this extreme flow rate the difference is not great enough to be seen in the pump bowl for ^{135}Xe , likely due to its long half-life.

Reproducing the matrix used for our solution of the system has provided some insight into the behavior. Suppose our isotopic vector, \mathbf{v} , contains the isotopes ^{135}I , ^{135m}Xe , and ^{135}Xe for the three locations in the loop. The vector \mathbf{v}^T is then given by

$$\mathbf{v}^T = \left[N_{I135}^{core} \quad N_{I135}^{PipeA} \quad N_{I135}^{PipeB} \quad N_{Xe135m}^{core} \quad N_{Xe135m}^{PipeA} \quad N_{Xe135m}^{PipeB} \quad N_{Xe135}^{core} \quad N_{Xe135}^{PipeA} \quad N_{Xe135}^{PipeB} \quad N_{U235}^{core} \right] \quad (5)$$

and we can write the row of the depletion matrix corresponding to ^{135}Xe in Pipe A as

$$\frac{dC_{PipeA}^{Xe135}}{dt} = \left[0 \quad +\lambda_{I135}^{Xe135} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad +\lambda_{Xe135m} \quad 0 \quad +f^{Core \rightarrow A} \quad -(\lambda_{Xe135} + \varepsilon_{multi-region} + f^{A \rightarrow B}) \quad 0 \quad 0 \right] \mathbf{v} \quad (6)$$

where λ_{I135}^{Xe135} is equivalent to the decay constant of ^{135}I multiplied by its branching ratio to ^{135}Xe (approximately 0.835). We can examine this matrix row with f equal to the volumetric flow rate from the MSRE, ν_{MSRE} , and for one tenth of that rate with ε with the same constant value of 0.00457 (ε_0), again in Pipe A.

$$\nu = \nu_{MSRE}: \quad [0 \quad 2.447\text{E-}05 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 7.556\text{E-}04 \quad 0 \quad 1.138\text{E-}01 \quad -1.881\text{E-}01 \quad 0 \quad 0] \quad (7)$$

$$\nu = 0.1\nu_{MSRE}: \quad [0 \quad 2.447\text{E-}05 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 7.556\text{E-}04 \quad 0 \quad 1.138\text{E-}02 \quad -2.294\text{E-}02 \quad 0 \quad 0] \quad (8)$$

The equilibrium concentrations involved in each of the regions are influenced by the ratio of production and removal terms in each region. The removal rate from each region will be determined largely by the salt flow rate, except for in Pipe A where the off-gas removal term ε does not vary across any of the runs. Thus, while the production and removal terms due to flow rate will have the same evolution for both Pipe A and Pipe B across the runs, Pipe A will always have a much larger overall removal term due to the presence of the OGS. This explanation is consistent with the results seen in Figures 2 and 3 but does not directly affect the percent difference between the one-region and multi-region OGS isotopics. Work is ongoing to fully characterize the behavior seen in a salt flow loop with respect to flow rate and off-gas transfer rate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

OpenMC simulations of a three-region MSR salt flow loop with varying salt flow rate indicate that, at the location of the off-gas transfer, isotopes with suitably long half-lives exhibit earlier convergence with respect to flow rate. As flow rate increases, all isotopes will tend to approach a homogeneous value throughout the loop. However, the presence of an additional transfer term in Pipe A causes that region to reach its equilibrium value at much lower flow rates than the other regions. This convergent behavior persists within about a magnitude of the flow rate present in the MSRE. Isotopes with converging concentrations at the location of off-gas transfer will also have convergent concentrations in the off-gas pumpbowl and throughout the OGS. This would allow for the flow loop to be ignored in modeling if the isotopes of interest have sufficiently long half-lives. However, examination of shorter-lived isotopes

in the OGS, such as ^{91}Kr , still requires discretization of the primary loop. An interesting extension of this work would be to determine the degree to which other regions of the loop have their concentration affected by the flow rate and development of a mathematical relationship to describe it. Additionally, future work will investigate the implementation of a “bypass loop” parallel to the primary loop from which species are transferred to the pump bowl, which more accurately represents the MSRE primary loop.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge that this work was funded through a grant from the State of Texas for the Digital Molten Salt Reactor Initiative.

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